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Impact of Disability among the Youth

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ABSTRACT

India is a country of 121 Crore Population, From them 2.68 Crore Persons are disabled, which Consist of near about 2.21% of the total population of the Country. The disabled population has both male and female and male consisting of 56% whereas female consist of 44% of the disable population of India if you compare the total population , male consist of 51% and female consist of 49% , while majority of them are disabled in rural areas , consisting of 69% of the population . Sustainable development in case of disability is the need of the hour and it may arise due to attitudinal, physical and financial factors. Government has taken steps to overcome barriers in health, rehabilitation, support, education, employment etc to the God children. National policy for youth with disabilities helps to identify them as effective human resources for the country and make an employment oriented and provide scope for equal justice for all in every sphere

INTRODUCTION

According to sustainable goals , UN -2015, Education of children with disabilities is now an integral part of international discourse and children with disabilities are the most excluded group of the education system As per WHO, disability is a concept which includes impairments, activity limitations and participations restrictions. According to WHO, youth with disabilities have less chance of getting jobs in better surroundings, seat in good schools or colleges. Article 24, CRPD, tells that they are included in the general education system and they are not distinguished as disabilities. Article 27, CRPD focuses on youth with disabilities having the right to go shoulder to shoulder with the common people in each and every sectors of the nations.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- ❖ To tackle the issues arising out of education for the disable children's.
- ❖ To Provide Employment opportunities for their lives and livelihoods.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

India is a young country with young revolving around the world and disability among the youth is an alarming topic which is treated as a secret weapon. The youth are the future of the country and any problem arising to them means problem to the whole of the nation, so solution to the problem is the need of the hour. India is a country of demographic divide so taking different issues from different parts of the country and making settlement of the issue is a really challenging job the job is challenging

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when it is inherent and difficult to comprehend. India needs to address lots of issues relating to health, education, safety and general aspects of the youth putting right policies in right frame for right communication to get better decision for implementation. They are the poorest and most marginalized group of people in the world that's why they are called as Divyanga

IMPACT OF DISABILITY ON YOUTH

Youth with disabilities remain under represented in higher educational institutions. Education is the weapon which can change the whole world. It reduces the knowledge gap affecting the impact of disability among the youth on school attendance, cross country parameters etc. More than 85% primary age children are out of the school as per the report issued by UNICEF. They find difficult in participation irrespective of socio economic and individual conditions.

While injustice in education and vocational training among themselves has affected them too much in employment opportunities. While government has taken steps in establishing national career center in each district specially for them, huge recruitment drive takes place for them but few get employment in this regard. The Details are as given below.

Particulars	Disability	No disability
Age 16 to 19	24.6%	33.1%
Age 20 to 24	40.9%	67.2%

Figure 1: Labour force Participation Rate

Source: Current population survey

Particulars	Disability	No disability
Age 16 to 19	46.5%	30.1%
Age 20 to 24	25.2%	23.2%

Figure 2: Unemployment rate

Source: Current population survey

PARTICULARS	MALES	FEMALES	BOTH
General	2.37	1.98	2.18
ST	2.18	1.92	2.05
SC	2.68	2.2	2.45
TOTAL	2.41	2.01	2.21
<p>The rate of persons is high in case of SC as compared to general, where as in case of males, SC percentage is higher than general. Same is the case in case of females. So in overall SC has a majority in case of disable proportion among all the groups</p> <p>Source: Data as per census 2011</p> <p>Figure 4: Proportion of Total Population</p>			
Person population as per census 2011	Classification of proportion of males and females		
Population	Male	Female	
121.08cr	63.22 cr	58.76cr	

Figure 3: Proportion of Disable Persons among Castes

Male dominating country but female proportion has increased since all times

Source: Data as per census 2011

Population	Male	Female
2.68cr	1.5 cr	1.18cr

Figure 5: Disable Person Population among Males and Females

More male are disabled than the female so job is essential for them to live for them and for their partners

Source: Data as per census 2011

Classification	Literate		Illiterate	
	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban
Male	58	73	42	28
Female	37	61	63	39
Both	49	67	51	33

Figure 6: Literate and Illiterate among Rural and Urban Youth with Disabilities

In case of rural, male are more affected than female. In urban also is the same case relating to literateration, while in illiterate the proportion is opposite and more in case of female

Source: Data as per census 2011

Barriers and Difficulties for Youth with Disability

- There has been Lack of available options among the disability's youth
- There has been very much mis information or no information regarding the prospective students or the family member's regarding youth who are with disabilities
- The family members are unaware about the procedures for getting their benefits
- There is Lack of communication and coordination between services, departments and ancillary
- Negligence in education sectors is to be streamlined
- There is less Funding for student disability
- More funding should be provided for mild intellectual disability, behavioral problems and learning difficulties
- Proper training to teachers and clerical staffs for the special schools and colleges
- Sensitization to general people and public as there are spicily children's of GOD creation
- Lack of transport facilities available for the movement of disable youth
- Equipment, technological aids and other devices are insufficient for the growth and development of disable youth

Suggestions to Minimize Problems for Youth with Disabilities

- Uniform policy for them should be made mandatory throughout the year
- Various incentives and scholarships to them should be provided on timely basis necessary for their study and livelihood
- Promotion of youth disable in international forum like games, sports and education
- As they are special children, they became special in each and every aspects of the curriculum
- Proper care and affection should be taken for them in recreational activities for their betterment
- Establishment of different ways of assessment for those who cannot participate in the common platform and relaxation for them also, so as to motivate them to achieve their goal

Conclusion

The paper concludes with the different issues regarding impact of disability among youth. The issues relates to proportion of male and female population, different group of caste structure in Indian scenario, different challenges of rural and urban literacy and illiteracy rates among youth with disability. The article also focuses on the barriers faced by them and steps taken to overcome it for the smooth conduct of their education pattern and employment opportunities .It also indicates that out of the total population , what is the proportion of males and female and out of that what is the share of male and female disable person . There are many issues and constraints which youth with disabilities faced but they are not properly taken care of. They are to be dealt with proper understanding and should not be neglected, they should take what is due to them. The figures 1 to 6 depicted the consequences of the issues and explains it in detail about the outcomes

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